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Qualitative Study on Jigsaw Instructional Strategy among Entrepreneurship Education Students at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: Features, Methods and Way Forward

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Abstract

This paper examined qualitative study on jigsaw instructional strategy among entrepreneurship education students at tertiary level of education in Nigeria: features, methods and way forward. It went further to discuss the topic under the following sub-headings: jig-saw cooperative learning features at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, jig-saw teaching technique of students in entrepreneurship at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, planning and preparation of jigsaw strategy at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, implementation of jigsaw instructional strategy at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, methods of teaching entrepreneurship at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, impact of jigsaw strategy on academic achievement of entrepreneurship education students at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. It was concluded that jig-saw has effects on academic achievement of entrepreneurship education students through: critical thinking and problem-solving skills, creativity and innovation, self-confidence, practical application of knowledge, communication and presentation skills, networking opportunities, interdisciplinary learning, team work skills. It was recommended that Jigsaw teaching method should be adopted in teaching entrepreneurship due to its effect on the acquisition of entrepreneurial concepts. Conducting training courses for the entrepreneurship teachers on the effective and proper use of the Jigsaw strategy in teaching entrepreneurship education among others.

Keywords: Jig Saw Cooperative learning, Academic Achievement, Entrepreneurship Education, Students, Tertiary Institutions

Introduction

Modebelu (2017) defines teaching as an activity comprising of a set of actions and programmes planned and targeted towards inculcating learning through conscious and deliberate efforts of a teacher. A teacher in this situation is expected to be a core professional who consciously and deliberately utilizes his or her wealth of experience, skills, competencies, attitudes, interest and mastery of the subject matter to facilitate learning in students. The product of teaching is learning activities that is, knowledge acquisition. Teaching and learning encounter is a two-directional affair whereby the teacher sends out the information while the learners communicate via evaluation, but this in and out processes can be good if teaching methods are appropriate. Ajoma (2017) views teaching method as professional technique that teachers adopt regularly in instructional exercises to enable them impart relevant knowledge and skills to the learner. Entrepreneurship teachers also employ various teaching methods to impact knowledge.

Jigsaw is one of the strategies of cooperative learning as it exercises the effort of working in teams for each of the students by reaching a favorable outcome (Halimah & Sukmayadi, 2019; Morera-Fernandez et al., 2020; Qiao & Jin, 2010; Vijayan et al., 2016). Jigsaw is formed when each student in a team becomes responsible for teaching other peers through a set of learnt materials (Jainal & Shahrill, 2021). It reduces students' reluctance in participating in class discussions and shown to create active learning''. Cooperative in general as described by the Search for Common Ground (2003) is a joint effort between parties to determine facts where discussions are made face-to-face which encouraged participation among everyone.

Moreover, respect is emphasized, decision is authorized by each of the members, the outcome need to be in satisfaction by everyone and the relationships are promoted through trust and being positive with each other.

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Being cooperative in classroom settings focused on students working together which could offer outcomes that enable the students learning to be more conducive and productive. The pedagogical practice of cooperative learning has increasingly attracted the attention of researchers. There is a large body of literature which indicates that students improved both academically and socially when students are given the opportunities to interact with each other to achieve shared goals. Cooperative learning approach provides a significant gap when compared to teacher centered learning. It enables students to work with their peers socially and practice the skills that are required for development (Dollard & Mahoney, 2010). Furthermore, using cooperative learning such as Jigsaw in the classroom have many effects such as improvements of academic performance, higher self-esteem and more positive views about school altogether (Winslow, 2020). Jainal, & Shahrill, (2021) mentioned that when students worked cooperatively, they put more effort into achieving positive outcomes because of the supportive relationships with their peers in constructive ways. In order for cooperative learning to be successful, five important features are crucial to be developed over time. They are positive interdependence, individual accountability, face-to-face interaction, social skills and group processing (Benek & Bezir Akcay, 2019; Jones & Jones, 2008). The use of cooperative learning strategies could assist students in the development of the 21st Century skills that comprised of collaboration, creativity, critical thinking and communication skills (Lai & Viering, 2012).

There are several cooperative learning strategies available, such as think-pair-share, thinking-aloud pair problem solving, the three-step interview, STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division), Jigsaw, TGT (Teams Games Tournaments) and GI (Group Investigation) (Astarini et al., 2019; Azmin, 2016; Benek & Bezir Akcay, 2019; Damit et al., 2015; Duraman et al., 2015; Halimah & Sukmayadi, 2019; Kani & Shahrill, 2015; Lee et al., 2018; Lim et al., 2016; Mahari et al., 2019; Morera-Fernandez et al., 2020; Simpol et al., 2018; Sulaiman & Shahrill, 2015; Vijayan et al., 2016). Cooperative in general is defined as providing group work where everyone participates on a collective task to help each other in completing the task provided to them by the teacher (Barron & Hammond, 2008). This will produce a great output because students are working together in achieving the shared goal agreed among each and every team member (Ransdell & Moberly, 2003). Similarly, Akinbolola (2009) stated that cooperative learning is an instructional approach that allows students with different working ability to work in teams in order to accomplish a purpose. This is because the setting of the classroom for cooperative learning to take place allows the students to freely set themselves for discussions in complementing each other's understanding (Veenman et al., 2002).

Academic achievement represents that which learners attain in his/her class room activities and ways to manage various teaching encounters expected of students by tutors. Ibrahim (2011) reports that in academic environment, progress is established by academic achievement. Morgan (2010) describes academic achievement as an evaluation technique whereby results of learners are collated via learners' task in a particular time. Therefore, it simply implies that performance quantifies the behaviours of a learner that is visible at a given time. Performance of students is highly vital because, this look like main standard whereby efficiency and progress of an institution of learning might be justified.

Academic achievement is an output of learning, in the sense that, level of attainment of educational aims and objectives of learners, instructors and schools/colleges. According to Jimoh, Idris and Olatunji (2016), academic achievement is the degree of success attained by students after being exposed to one form of learning or the other. Jimoh (2014) confirms that achievement in academic is the extent of progress achieved by learners in their course of study. Ezenwosu and Nworgu (2013) noted that academic achievement is commonly measured using classroom exercise, assignment and continuous assessment as well as internal and external examination. It can be used to indicate students' level of success in a particular task students were previously exposed to and it can also be used as indices for determining students' capability to effectively undertake another task (Jimoh, 2014).

Oguntimehin (2017) stated that the rationale for the inclusion of entrepreneurship curricula in universities, polytechnics and colleges is to help graduates to acquire increased understanding of entrepreneurship, equip them with entrepreneurial approach to the world of work and prepare them to act as entrepreneurs and managers of new businesses. Entrepreneurship Education has been view as a systematic training and instruction that transmit entrepreneurial knowledge and development of skills in students. Entrepreneurship education is meant to change students' behaviour pattern in the desired direction. Therefore, Entrepreneurship education is a continuing development of relevant entrepreneurial skills and habits whose understanding and application enable the Business students to contribute meaningfully towards the growth and development of Nigerian economy.

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Similarly, Entrepreneurship education is the process of imparting knowledge and teaching skills to potential entrepreneurs on how to venture into business that is relatively small in nature for future development or advancement (Aminu, 2012). According to Adiele (2010) entrepreneurial education is designed to communicate and inculcate competencies, skills and values needed to recognize business opportunity, organize and start new business venture. It is regarded as a vital tool for reduction of unemployment.

Jig-Saw Cooperative Learning Features at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Cooperative learning is an instructional strategy in which small groups of students work together to achieve a common goal. This approach fosters collaboration, communication, and mutual support among students. Examples of some key features of cooperative learning are:

1. **Positive Interdependence:** Students are dependent on each other to achieve a common goal. Success is linked to the success of the group, fostering a sense of collective responsibility.
2. **Individual Accountability:** Each student in the group is responsible for their own learning and contributes to the groups success. Individual assessments may be used to ensure that each student is actively participating and mastering the material.
3. **Face to Face Interaction:** Students work together in small face to face groups. Interaction is essential for communication, sharing ideas and resolving conflicts within the group.
4. **Interpersonal and Small Group Skills:** Cooperative learning enhances social skills, such as communication, leadership and conflict resolution. Students learn to work effectively in a team, respecting diverse opinion and backgrounds.
5. **Group Process:** Groups periodically reflects on their performance and make adjustments to improve their collaboration. This reflective process helps students identify what is working well and what can be improved within the group.
6. **Promotion of Critical Thinking:** Cooperative learning activities often involve problem solving and critical thinking. Students learn to analyze information, evaluate ideas and apply their knowledge in real world situations.
7. **Heterogeneous Grouping:** Groups are often formed with students of varying abilities, backgrounds and skills. Heterogeneous grouping promotes diversity and provides opportunities for peer teaching and learning.
8. **Promotion of a Positive Learning Environment:** Cooperative learning fosters a supportive and positive classroom atmosphere. Students feel a sense of belonging and are more motivated to participate actively in their learning.
9. **Teacher as a Facilitator:** The role of the teacher shifts from a lecturer to a facilitator. The teacher provides guidance, support and structure, but the emphasis is on student led learning.
10. **Integration of Individual and Group Goals:** Individual and group goals are aligned to create a cohesive learning experience. The success of the individual is connected to the success of the group, and vice versa.
11. **Promotion of Social Skills:** Cooperative learning helps students develop social skills, such as communication, teamwork, and conflict resolution. Interacting with peers in a collaborative setting prepares students for real-world social interactions.
12. **Varied Learning Activities:** Cooperative learning can be applied to a variety of learning activities, including discussions, projects, problem solving task and more. This versatility allows teachers to adapt the cooperative learning approach to different subjects and learning objectives.

Jig-Saw Teaching Technique of Students in Entrepreneurship at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The jigsaw teaching strategy is a collaborative learning approach, which was first developed by Elliot Aronson and his students at the University of Texas and the University of California in the early 1970s. In jigsaw, each student in a group takes responsibility for one chunk of the content, then teaches it to the other group members. Like the pieces of a jigsaw puzzle, students fit their individual chunks together to form a complete body of knowledge. The goal of the approach is to study the learning material in groups to achieve specific objectives. This strategy draws a direct image of a jigsaw puzzle where each student represents a piece of the puzzle. As the final image of a puzzle constructed from fitting together separate pieces, each student presents his/her assigned task to complete the puzzle.

Jigsaw strategy is based on “cooperation by design” where no student can succeed completely unless everyone works well together as a team. This understanding leads students to value each other as contributors to a shared task. Jigsaw strategy empowers students to take charge of their learning, and aids retention, peer tutoring,

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communication skills and retrieval of concepts (Sabbah, 2016). In studies comparing Jigsaw with traditional direct instruction, students taught with the Jigsaw method demonstrated increased feelings of autonomy, competence, and intrinsic motivation (Hänze & Berger, 2007).

Imagine you are an entrepreneurship teacher who wants to do an overview of different types of business using the jigsaw method. You can divide your content into these chunks; tailoring, hair dressing, soap making, and bead making. In this case, you will need 4 home groups, and 4 expert groups to study each chunk as displayed in Figure 1. You will assign each expert group one chunk to study. The student in the expert group will be responsible to teach that chunk to the rest of the students in the home group.

Figure 1. Jigsaw Approach

(Adapted from Jigsaw Cooperative Approach in Professional Studies)

Planning and Preparation of Jigsaw strategy at tertiary level of education in Nigeria

1. The teacher selects the content to be taught for the next lecture.
2. The content is divided into subtopics (according to the number of the students in a group).
3. The teacher should prepare clear instructions for students, and she/he should also explain the critical terminology so that students can understand the topic easily

TIP: Jigsaw works best when you have the same number of students in each team (Newbury, 2015)

Implementation of Jigsaw instructional strategy at tertiary level of Education in Nigeria

1. Divide students into groups of 4 to 6.
2. Divide your content into 4 or 6 chunks (i.e. the number of the chunks depends on the number of the students in each group).
3. Give each student in the home group a different chunk to master. Make sure they read and study their chunk individually.
4. Have students meet in expert groups. Gathering with all the other students assigned with the same chunk will give them the chance to compare their ideas and work together to get prepared. This also helps to enhance their communication skills and help them to solve any queries. This is particularly helpful for the students who find it challenging to understand the task on their own.
5. Students in the expert groups then return to their home groups to present their chunk to other members of the team. Meanwhile, others in the group listen carefully, take notes and ask a lot of questions. Here, students are accountable for individual learning and the success of the group.
6. Walk around the classroom to observe and offer any kind of help if necessary.
7. At the end of the class, give a quiz on the material to make sure all students got a basic understanding of all the material.

TIP: In each home group, appoint one of the students to be the discussion leader, on a rotating basis. It helps the groups run more effectively (Newbury, 2015).

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Methods of Teaching Entrepreneurship at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The Consortium for Entrepreneurship Education (2008) defines entrepreneurship education as one which seeks to prepare people, especially the youth, to be responsible, enterprising individuals who become entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers and who contribute to economic development and sustainable communities. Such education is not just based on text-book courses; instead students are immersed in real-life learning experiences where they have an opportunity to take risks, manage the results and learn from the outcomes. By implication, entrepreneurship education at undergraduate level is expected to inspire and motivate students to develop knowledge and skills of self-reliance, fashion for venture creation and innovative skills for sustainable development. Students, irrespective of their gender and the location of their institutions, who have acquired all these skills through entrepreneurship education are likely to be positioned not only for self-reliance but also to create jobs for others.

This collaborative learning technique helps to engage all students in their learning by motivating students to learn a topic or skill well enough to demonstrate it and teach it to their peers. Jigsaw is “also an efficient strategy for extending the breadth, depth, and scope of learning because students learn and teach multiple topics simultaneously during the same class session” (Barkeley, Cross and Major, 2014).

Impact of Jigsaw Strategy on Academic Achievement of Entrepreneurship Education Students at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

By structuring small group discussions and assignment deliverables, Jigsaw as a collaborative learning tool also helps to foster a welcoming and equitable learning experience for students (Theobald et al. 2017). Entrepreneurship education can have several positive impacts on students, both academically and personally through:

1. **Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving Skills:** Entrepreneurship education often encourages students to think critically and develop problem-solving skills. This can enhance their ability to analyze situations, make decisions, and solve problems, which are valuable skills in academic settings. These skills can contribute to academic success by promoting a deeper understanding of subject matter and the ability to apply knowledge in diverse situations.
2. **Creativity and Innovation:** Entrepreneurship programs often foster creativity and innovation. Students learn to think outside the box, come up with new ideas, and explore innovative solutions. These qualities can positively influence academic performance, especially in subjects that require creative thinking.
3. **Self-Confidence:** Entrepreneurship education can boost students' self-confidence by challenging them to take risks and step out of their comfort zones. Increased confidence can lead to better academic performance as students become more willing to participate in class discussions and take on challenging tasks.
4. **Practical Application of Knowledge:** Entrepreneurship education is often hands-on and practical. Students may have the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios. This practical application can deepen their understanding of academic subjects and make learning more engaging.
5. **Communication and Presentation Skills:** Many entrepreneurship programs emphasize communication and presentation skills, which are valuable in academic and professional settings. Improved communication skills can enhance students' ability to express themselves clearly in essays, presentations, and discussions.
6. **Networking Opportunities:** Entrepreneurship programs often provide networking opportunities with professionals, mentors, and fellow students. Networking can open doors to academic resources, research opportunities, and collaborative projects, positively impacting academic achievement.
7. **Interdisciplinary Learning:** Entrepreneurship often involves knowledge from various disciplines, such as marketing, finance, and management. Integrating these diverse fields in an entrepreneurial context can lead to a more holistic understanding of academic concepts.
8. **Teamwork Skills:** Entrepreneurship education often involves collaborative projects, fostering teamwork and communication skills. These soft skills are valuable not only in entrepreneurial endeavors but also in academic settings.

Conclusion

Cooperative learning is recommended for teachers to use as part of their teaching strategy because it provides ample evidence of support in students learning. Students participate more and since members in a group consisted of heterogeneous ability, provided that teachers structure the group properly, it enhances students learning with better understanding. As a cautionary advice, teachers who decide to use Jigsaw as their teaching strategy, they

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need to have adequate understanding of how the method works. Besides, teachers will need to have excellent resources and knowledge of why and how they want to incorporate this learning strategy into their teaching. By doing so, the learning process will be more organized. In addition, teachers need to emphasize to students the importance of equal participation, being interdependent and accountable, and to have cohesion with each team member. Teachers need to inform their students to take control of their learning by becoming actively involved. This would ensure the success of the cooperative learning being incorporated. Teachers will also need to provide students with the opportunity to evaluate their own ability during the group work to ensure that the five features to cooperative learning had been achieved.

Recommendations

Based on the study of jigsaw, the following recommendations are made:

1. Adopting a teaching method by using (Jigsaw) in teaching entrepreneurship due to its effect on the acquisition of entrepreneurial concepts.
2. Conducting training courses for the entrepreneurship teachers on the effective and proper use of the Jigsaw strategy in teaching entrepreneurship education.
3. Conducting further studies and research on using the Jigsaw strategy in teaching other courses, such as Accounts and marketing, and studying students' attitudes towards using them.
4. The teachers need to diversify the method of teaching entrepreneurship such as jigsaw as it will assist in higher academic achievement of students.
5. Jigsaw technique should be adopted in universities by business education teachers for teaching of financial accounting so as to improve the academic achievement of students.
6. Governments should employ qualified hands to teach various vocational subjects because it is only a qualified teacher with effective teaching method that can remedy students' poor academic achievement in entrepreneurship and other vocational subjects.
7. All learners should be given equal opportunity and the same level of encouragement irrespective of the gender.

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